

Synopsis of the Thesis

Silicon Integrated Mechanical Sensors of Control, Monitoring, Regulation Systems for Temperature Range (0 ÷ 300)°C

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by

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ABSTRACT

The main part of scientific material of PhD thesis "Silicon Integrated Mechanical Sensors of Control, Monitoring, Regulation Systems for Temperature Range ($0 \div 300$) $^{\circ}C$ " in the specialty 05.13.05 "Elements and devices of computer engineering and control systems" is presented. The main results: the regular influence of physical and geometrical parameters on the temperature dependence of the insulating properties of p-n-junctions, allowing to expand the working temperature range up to $+210^{\circ}C$, has been established; the way of further expansion of the temperature range up to $300^{\circ}C$ by eliminating the insulating p-n junction has been proposed, grounded and experimentally evaluated; the methods of improving the accuracy of silicon integrated converters have been developed and experimentally evaluated. On the basis of this work, total pressure and low-frequency acceleration transducers were created, meeting the requirements and operating conditions for model tests of modern and advanced rocket engines. The efficiency and great practical importance of the work were confirmed by the results of the introduction into the experimental and design work of the organizations of the Ministry of General Machine-Building

Keywords: *Semiconductor measuring transducers, Piezoresistive effect in p-type silicon, silicon sensor, pressure, LF-acceleration.*

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

The introduction substantiates the relevance of the topic of the dissertation work, formulates scientific novelty and the provisions submitted by the author for defense.

1.1 Relevance of problem

At the present stage of development of our industry, the parameters of control system elements (CS), system control (MS), system regulation (RS) largely depend on the quality of products, improvement of their technical characteristics. Depending on the purpose of the system, the elements divide into four functional groups of devices: (1) for receiving information about processes and objects; (2) to receive, transform and transmit information; (3) for processing, storing information, and forming control commands; (4) devices for using command information. Information acquisition tools (1) are the largest group and usually make up more than half of the assortment of all technical means of the system. When solving industrial problems, the main components of this group of elements are primary transducers (sensors) of mechanical quantities (pressure, acceleration, impact, etc.). Typical for the industry sensors of mechanical quantities VT, LH, ANS, etc. They have significant disadvantages: high weight and overall dimensions, low sensitivity, the high labor intensity of manufacture, driving during operation. Their constructive-technological solutions probably will not allow to significantly improve technical indicators in the future. For this reason, existing primary information transducers do not fundamentally solve a number of current industrial problems, especially in the creation of new products.[1] One of these tasks relates to the management of research tests of the RD-170 (11D521) and RD-171 (11D520) reusable LPRE units. The problem here comes from obtaining accurate information about the pressure fields in LPRE units. Ranges of measured pressures from 0 – 1 atm to 0 – 10 atm. In this case, the intrinsic error of the pressure sensors should not exceed $\pm 1\%$. The second problem includes obtaining accurate information about vibration modes, parameters of dynamic stability, dynamic overloads on nodes, and power elements. Measured acceleration ranges from $0 \pm 1 g$ to $0 \pm 10 g$, frequency spectrum 0 – 300 Hz. The intrinsic error of accelerometers should not exceed $\pm 5\%$.

1.2 Methods of research

Theoretical studies use methods of mathematical modeling, the theories of transport phenomena, contact phenomena, and the piezoresistive effect in semiconductors. The author experimentally determined the electrophysical characteristics of the piezoresistive channels, the material of the elastic element, the insulating p-n junction, and the metrological characteristics of the integrated piezoresistive transducer (IPT). The methods of probability theory and mathematical statistics confirmed the results of the experiments.

1.3 Scientific novelty.

The scientific novelty of the work consists in the development of physical and functional models and principles of constructing monolithic silicon integrated strain resistor transducers of small sensors mechanical values for the operating temperature range $0 - 300^{\circ}C$.

1.4 The new results:

the natural influences of physical and geometric parameters on the temperature dependence of the insulating properties of the IPT p-n junctions at temperatures more than $0 - +100^{\circ}C$;

a physical and functional model of the primary deformation transducer with a part of the elastic element material electrically connected to the bridge measuring circuit;

the principles of designing precision monolithic IPT of small-sized pressure and acceleration sensors for the operating temperature range of $0 - 300^{\circ}C$, including minimization of the intrinsic error of the IPT by the identity of the electrical parameters of the bridge measuring circuit;

minimization of the additional temperature error of the IPT with an insulating p-n junction in the $0 - +200^{\circ}C$ range by using the regular temperature changes of the electrophysical characteristics of silicon piezoresistive p-type channels and passive regulating resistive elements;

minimization of the additional temperature error of IPT by using a part of the elastic transducer element as a regulating element of the output signal temperature dependence for the $0 - 300^{\circ}C$ range.

1.5 Practical value and implementation of results

Developed unified series of microminiature IPT SIAP 408854.001 for small pressure sensors from $0 - 0.1$ atm to $0 - 10$ atm, small-sized LF-accelerometers (LF-Low Fre-

quency) ANPPE SIAP.402139.001 for measurements of low-frequency accelerations from $0 \pm 1 g$ to $0 \pm 30 g$ in the frequency range $0 - 300 Hz$.

1.6 Approbation

The All-Union Conference "Methods and means of tensometry and their application in the national economy" in Sverdlovsk 1989 ; Scientific conferences of faculty and post-graduate students of the MSFU (Moscow State Forest University) 1983, 1984, 1985.

1.7 Publications

The author outlined the main content and results of the work in 9 articles and defended three certificates of authorship.

1.8 The volume of work

The thesis work consists of an introduction, four chapters, and a conclusion, on 83 pages of typescript, 6 tables, 35 figures, a list of literature comprising 84 titles and applications.

1.9 The main provisions:

extension of the upper limit of the working temperature range of silicon integrated strain gauge transducers of mechanical quantities, with an insulating p-n junction, to values over $+200^{\circ}C$ by reducing the area, the transition perimeter, and the number of angles in the topological structure of the elements;

the physical and functional model of the transducer of mechanical quantity without insulating p-n junction, allowing at the expense of selection of electro-physical characteristics of Si piezoresistive channels and Si elastic element to extend the upper limit of a range of working temperatures to values more than $300^{\circ}C$;

a method to compensate for the additional temperature error in the temperature range $-60 - 325^{\circ}C$ of silicon mechanical magnitude sensors by electrically connecting part of the resilient element material to a bridge circuit and selecting the resistivity of the resilient element material in the range $(0.5 \div 10)\Omega \cdot cm$.

CHAPTER 2

Status analysis of silicon integrated piezoresistive transducers for the operating temperature range of 0-300°C

The author presents the known designs of sensors of mechanical quantities for a range of $(0 \div 300)^\circ\text{C}$. Fig.2.1 shows a typical conversion circuit in mechanical transducers. The silicon element attached to the housing parts (BP) through a layer of compound (CL) is part of a generalized IPT design [2, 3]. The IPT "CL — BP" circuit provides mechanical isolation of the silicon cell from downstream body parts or test fixtures. The silicon cell contains a rigid base (RB), an elastic element (EE), a layer (IL) that insulates the silicon piezoresistive channels (PCH) with pads (CA) of the full-bridge measuring circuit (BC) and control resistive elements (RCE) of the thermal compensation circuit (TCC). The SiO₂ (M) masking layer, with the aluminum pads, tracks, and thin-film control resistors, protects the "RB — EE — PCH — CA" structure of the silicon element from the planar side. Silicon piezoresistive channels (PCH) with contact pads (CA) of the full-bridge measuring circuit (BC) and the controlling resistive elements (RCE) of the thermocompensation circuit (TCC) make up the integrated piezoresistive transducer's measurement circuit (MC).

Known design solutions for IPT comprise the following groups: heterogeneous with dielectric IL [4]; monolithic with insulating elements BC p-n junction [5]; monolithic without insulating p-n junction [6]; with lumped parameters BC, where the PCH conductivity is more than 10 times the EE conductivity; monolithic without isolating p-n junction with distributed parameters. The type of insulation determines the operating temperature range of the IPT. When isolating BC with p-n-junctions, the critical value of junction insulation resistance determines the upper value of the operating temperature range.

For the dielectric insulated PCH, the two "extremes" on the temperature dependence of resistance define the operating temperature range: 1 — a minimum due to a change in the mechanism of scattering of charge carriers [7]; 2 — maximum, caused by the appearance of intrinsic conductivity [8, 9].

Design solutions of heterogeneous IL dielectric sensors in the article [4] have large overall dimensions (more than $15 \times 15 \times 15$ mm) and mass (more than 30 g). Reducing

the overall dimensions and mass will significantly increase the labor intensity of their manufacture and the systematic component of the intrinsic error (bias error) due to: high-temperature gas profiling of sapphire before RCH and other operations of *BC* and *TC* element formation in heteroepitaxial IPTs (SOS — IPT); non-reproducibility of geometrical dimensions of *EE* and *RB* during isotropic etching of polysilicon in IPT with *SiO2* (EPIC — IPT) and during sintering of silicon wafers in IPT with low-temperature glass *IL* (SIS — IPT); low accuracy of the reproduction of the geometric dimensions of *RCH* from mesa — structures. Promising for small-sized sensors is the design of IPT with monocrystalline silicon "EE — RB" and *PCH*, connected and electrically isolated from each other by a layer of glass, consistent with the silicon on the coefficient of thermal expansion [10]. The efficient production technology of monolithic IPTs predetermines the miniaturization of sensors. Here: the advantages of monocrystalline silicon, which is the material of *EE* and *PCH*, are widely used; mechanical properties of *RB*, *EE*, *IL*, *PCH* materials are consistent; the systematic component of the intrinsic error (bias error) of sensors is significantly reduced due to the joint use of group technological processes of silicon micromachining and formation of elements and conductors with high reproducibility of geometric dimensions and ratios [11].

Fig. 2.1 Structure diagram of the measurement conversion of a mechanical quantity into an electrical signal by an IPT transducer. 1- for inertial sensors; 2 - for IPT with distributed parameters.

Research and analysis identified two IPT designs: with lumped parameters, where the CAs are interconnected by piezoresistive channels electrically isolated from the elastic element; with distributed parameters, where CAs are located directly on the

elastic element without PCH or inside one PCH (similar to a Hall-transducer). Insulating properties of the p-n junction at temperatures above $+100^{\circ}C$ are not sufficiently studied. The temperature limit of $+125^{\circ}C$ indicated in the literature is not the limit for the operation of monolithic IPT with insulating p-n junction. At temperatures, when the insulation resistance of the p-n junction decreases to the value of $R_i^{IL} \leq 200R_{in}^{BC}$ (R_{in}^{BC} — input resistance BC), sharp changes of temperature dependences of IPT parameters are observed. The use of monolithic monocrystalline IPTs without isolating the p-n junction allows expanding the operating temperature range. The upper-temperature limit rises to $+150^{\circ}C$ for IPT with BC with lumped parameters. For such a design, the resistivity of the EE material must be $\rho^{ee} > 20 \Omega \cdot cm$. The reason for the range limitation the decrease of sensitivity due to the sharp decrease of resistance of the part of EE material, connected in parallel to the output and input of BC when the intrinsic conductivity of silicon appears.

Using an IPT with distributed parameters increases the upper-temperature range limit to $400^{\circ}C$. The paper [12] describes a transducer design where the contacts directly on the elastic element without piezoresistive channels determine the MC. But in this case, the IPT sensitivity is more than 3 times less because in the EE body the current is firstly directed along with the non-tensile crystallographic directions, secondly distributed in the Z direction normal to the planar surface of the bending EE. The upper limit of the operating temperature range of the EE monocrystalline silicon elastic element (EE) is $600^{\circ}C$.

The calculation of the IPT design should be based on the data obtained within a stable manufacturing technology. The temperature range of experimental studies of the electrophysical characteristics of PCH has the following limitations: for diffusion layers $125^{\circ}C$, for ion implantation $100^{\circ}C$. Use of diffusion layers with the value of average resistivity $\bar{\rho}^{ch} = (2 \div 8) \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot cm$ will allow to reduce geometric dimensions of PCH and complementary temperature error of IPT when supplying BC with stabilized current. The doping dose that provides the smallest scattering of the electrical resistivity of PCH is the area of study of ion-alloyed layers. In silicon IPTs, workable in the range of $0 - 300^{\circ}C$, it is advisable to form aluminum ohmic contacts. In the known studies there is no data on the influence of the contact area on the normalized null output BC K_{mc0} .

IPTs are tuned by internal regulating passive resistive elements, located in the vicinity of the PCH. The thin-film alloy PC-1004 is used, which is operable at temperatures above $+100$ — and is characterized by a negative temperature coefficient of resistance.

To achieve the goal it was necessary to solve the following main tasks: to investigate the models of isolation of p-type elements of monolithic IPTs from the elastic element EE by the depleted charge carriers layer of the p-n junction at temperatures higher than $+100$; study the influence of minimization of geometrical dimen-

sions of BC IPC topological structure at values of total p-n junction area less than $2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2$ on the upper value of operating temperature range and value and temperature dependence of $K_{mc0}(T)$; to investigate the regularities of changes in the electrophysical characteristics of a monolithic IPT with an insulating p-n junction in the temperature range of $0 - +250^\circ\text{C}$, when the formation of PCH and CA is carried out by a stationary technological process: a) by boron diffusion for values of average resistivity $\bar{\rho}^{ch} = (2 \div 8) \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ by boron ion implantation with doping $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ study principles of modeling IPT with distributed parameters without p-n junctions, where PCH conductivity exceeds EE conductivity by 2 to 10 times; to study the electrophysical characteristics of IPT with distributed parameters in the temperature range of $(0 \div 300)^\circ\text{C}$; to investigate and develop methods of minimization of intrinsic and additional temperature error of IPT in the operating temperature range of $0 - 300$; specific design solutions of small-sized pressure sensors with intrinsic error of $\pm 1\%$ and acceleration sensors with intrinsic error of $\pm 5\%$ for testing industrial products and obtaining information on processes and objects with ambient temperature variations in the range of $(0 \div 300)^\circ\text{C}$; investigate the possibility of developing a silicon IPT design with a monocrystalline silicon base (EE-RB) and monocrystalline silicon measurement circuit elements (PCH) connected to each other and electrically isolated from each other by a layer of glass.

CHAPTER 3

Principles of monolithic IPT modeling for the 0-300°C temperature range

The section contains the results of theoretical and experimental studies of physical and functional models of monolithic IPT for the temperature range of 0 – 300°C.

3.1 Monolithic IPTs with isolating p-n junction

The condition when the shunt effect of the EE resistance on one of the MC's arms will change the transfer coefficient $K_{mc} = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}}$ by 1% of the nominal value determines the upper limit of the temperature range T_{max} of the monolithic IPT with an insulating p-n junction. In this case, the insulation resistance R_i^{IL} decreases to a critical value R_{imin}^{IL} . Modeling and experimental studies are related to the study of temperature dependences of the p-n junction parameter J_{rev} (reverse current density) [13]. Simplification of modeling and increasing the accuracy of experimental studies of miniature IPTs with an extended operating temperature range required the following design solutions. Anisotropic etching of silicon wafers with orientation in the plane (001) determines the highest accuracy of geometric parameters of the elastic element EE. [14]. In the future, this method can find usage in manufacturing processes for most of the EE types used (diaphragm, beam). The channels of piezoresistors doped with an acceptor impurity are arranged parallel and perpendicular to the EE boundaries (along with directions of the form [011]). The same stress state of EE regions (at small deformations), with longitudinal and transverse PCH channels, causes proportional changes in resistances, which are close to each other in magnitude and opposite in sign. The following design requirements approximate the value and temperature dependence of the normalized null output of MC K_{mc0} to zero values:

- minimum scatter of values of electrical resistance of PCH and identity of their temperature dependences;
- insignificant value and minimal scatter of the initial strain EE values in the areas of PCH location and the identity of their temperature dependences;
- equality of all thermal resistances in the PCH-EE heat sink chain;
- minimization of the temperature gradient in the plane of PCH placement on EE

Fig.3.1 shows the design of the strain test transducer. The plane (001) defines the surface of the silicon monocrystal structure of the elastic element EE. The MC contains equal square contact areas of size b . The centers at the vertices of the square of size a are interconnected by four PCH channels of width d_{ch} (longitudinal R_1^{ch}, R_3^{ch} and transverse R_2^{ch}, R_4^{ch}). The contact areas CA and piezoresistive PCH channels are formed by local doping of the monocrystalline silicon wafer with boron admixture. The MC elements are arranged in an EE body of thickness H_{EE}

The standard resistance values of the bridge circuit R_{in} for strain gauge sensors of mechanical quantities are in the range from 50Ω to 1000Ω [15]. With $d_{ch} = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}$ and surface resistance of ion-alloyed layer $R_s = 85 \text{ ohm}/\square$, the value of channel length $(a - b)$ is in the range $(10 \div 200) \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}$, and the total area of p-n junction, with $b = 40 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}$ is $A_{p-n} = (0.5 \div 2) \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$. In this case, if the size of the elasto-deformable part EE is more than $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}$, we can assume that the equality $\varepsilon_{x2} = \varepsilon_{x4} = \varepsilon_{x0}$ is fulfilled. Then for the chosen design the conversion characteristic will be:

$$K_{mc} = \frac{V_{out}}{V_{in}} = 0.5 \cdot K_{\parallel} \cdot \varepsilon_{x0} \left(1 - \frac{K_{\perp}}{K_{\parallel}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where K_{\parallel} and K_{\perp} are respectively longitudinal and transverse piezoresistive coefficients of silicon PCH; ε_{x0} is the value of strain EE in the geometric centers of strain gauge channels $R_1^{ch}, R_2^{ch}, R_3^{ch}, R_4^{ch}$. For the selected MC, the total area A_{p-n} and the perimeter P_{p-n} of the insulating p-n junction are determined by the relations:

$$A_{p-n} = 4 \cdot [b^2 + d_{ch} \cdot (a - b)] ; \quad (2)$$

$$P_{p-n} = 8 \cdot (a + b - d_{ch}) \quad (3)$$

Such MC will allow approaching zero value and temperature changes of normalized null output, $K_{mc0}(T) = 0$, and to reduce the total area of the insulating $p - n$ junction to values $A_{p-n} < 2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2$. The temperature at which the insulation resistance reaches the value R_{per}^{IL} determines the upper limit of the operating temperature range $T = T_{per}$ for MCs isolated from the EE by a $p - n$ junction layer [16].

$$R_{per}^{IL} = 2.5 \cdot 10^3 \cdot R_{in} \quad (4)$$

With a further increase in temperature, the shunt effect of the resistance part of the EE material on one of the arms of the MC may change the value of the transfer coefficient by more than 1% relative to its nominal value.

Fig. 3.1 Topological structure of IPT deformation for research and development of modeling principles of the structure operable in the operating temperature range of 0-300°C.

The following conditions determine the calculated dependence of inverse current density $J_{rev}(T)$ on temperature and the upper limit of the operating temperature range of the monolithic IPT:

(1) The dependence $J_{rev}(T)$ is determined from the relationship for the reverse current in [[17]] :

$$I_{rev} = I_{0gen} + I_{Sgen} + I_d \quad (5)$$

where $I_{0gen} = \frac{1}{2}q\frac{n_i}{\tau_0}d_{p-n} \cdot A_{p-n}$ is the carrier generation current in the carrier-poor p-n junction region in the EE volume; n_i is the carrier concentration in the native semiconductor; τ_0 is the carrier lifetime in the p-n junction region; d_{p-n} is the width of the p-n junction region; q is the elementary charge;

$I_{Sgen} = \frac{1}{2}qS_0 \cdot n_i \cdot d_{p-n} \cdot P_{p-n}$ is the current of charge carrier generation in the carrier-poor region of the p-n junction at the EE surface; S_0 is the surface recombination rate; P_{p-n} is the perimeter of the p-n junction;

$I_d = \frac{qn_i^2 L_p}{\tau_p N_n} \cdot A_{p-n}$ diffusion component of reverse current; L_p - diffusion length of minority charge carriers in the EE body; N_n - concentration of impurity in the EE body; $n_i(T) = n_{i0} \cdot e^{21.3(1-\frac{T_0}{T})}$ is the concentration of free charge carriers; $\tau_p(T)$ is the lifetime of minority charge carriers in the EE body from the graph in Fig. $3\mu_p(T) = \mu_{p0} \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^{2.5}$ is the mobility for minority charge carriers in the EE body; $L_p(T) =$

Fig. 3.2 Temperature dependence of the lifetime of the main carriers [9].

$\left(\frac{\mu_p(T) \cdot \tau_p(T) \cdot \kappa \cdot T}{q}\right)^{1/2}$ — diffusion length for minority charge carriers in the EE body;
 S_0 — does not change with temperature and is equal to the maximum value of $S_0 = 1 \cdot 10^4$ cm/sec.

(2) The p-n junction is sharp, asymmetric, stepped, p-n type (i.e., $\bar{\rho}_{ch} \ll \rho_{EE}$) with the width of the bulk charge region in the EE body equal to

$$d_{p-n} \approx 3,65 \cdot 10^3 \left(\frac{V_{rev}}{N_e^{EE}}\right)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

and uniform distribution of volume charges along the metallurgical boundary of the transition.

(3) In the topological MC structure in Fig. 3.1 the geometrical parameter b is given a constant value equal to $b = 40 \cdot 10^{-4}$ cm. For calculations it is chosen that $b = d_{ch}$, then the change of the area of the insulating p-n junction is possible only by changing the length of PCH $l_{ch} = (a - b)$. The ratio of the perimeter of p-n junction P_{p-n} to the area A_{p-n} is a constant value equal to

$$K_{p-n} = \frac{P_{p-n}}{A_{p-n}} = 500 \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

(4) The reverse bias voltage of the p-n junction and the supply voltage of the MC is $V_{rev} = V_{in} = 5V$.

(5) The boundary values of the resistivities EE are determined by the values:

$\rho_{ee1} = 20 \Omega \cdot cm$, from the graph in Fig.3.2 the intrinsic conductivity temperature $+150^\circ C$;

$\rho_{ee1} = 0.5 \Omega \cdot cm$ is a calculated value of breakdown voltage of p-n junction in EE volume chosen equal to $V_{br} = 10 \cdot V_{in}$ from the ratio :

$$V_{br} = 10 \cdot V_{in} = 86 \cdot \rho_{ee} \quad (8)$$

$\rho_{ee1} = 4.5 \Omega \cdot cm$ is a standard value of resistivity of silicon wafers in the manufacture of IPT.

(6) Initial temperature value $T_0 = 293K$. Taking into account the selected initial data and calculated relations, the temperature dependence of the reverse current density VAC of isolating p-n junction IPT is defined by the following expression:

$$J_{rev} = q \cdot a_{p-n} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\tau_p(T)} + S_0 \cdot K_{p-n} \right) \cdot e^{22.2 \cdot \left(\frac{T-293}{T} \right)} + q \cdot \left[\left(\frac{k \cdot \mu_{p0}}{q \cdot \tau_p(T)} \right)^{1/2} \cdot \left(\frac{113.7}{T} \right)^3 \cdot P_n \cdot e^{22.2 \cdot \left(\frac{T-293}{T} \right)} \right] \cdot e^{22.2 \cdot \left(\frac{T-293}{T} \right)} \quad (9)$$

where $a_{p-n} = \frac{d_{p-n} \cdot n_{i0}}{2}$ is the parameter characterizing the concentration of native charge carriers n_{i0} in the p-n junction region at temperature $T = 293^\circ K$;

$P_n = \frac{n_{i0}^2}{N_{0}^{ee}}$ is the concentration of nonessential charge carriers in the EE body at temperature $T = 293^\circ K$;

$k = 1,38 \cdot 10^{-23} J/K$ is the Boltzmann constant.

To experimentally verify the calculations, test samples of IPT with beam elastic element were made from n-type monocrystalline silicon with orientation (001) and resistivity $\rho_{ee3} = 4.5 \Omega \cdot cm$. The geometric parameters of the MC topological structure are as follows:

$$b = 40 \cdot 10^{-4} cm ; b = d_{ch} ; a = 3b ;$$

$$A_{p-n} = 1.92 \cdot 10^{-4} cm^2 ; K_{p-n} = 500 cm^{-1} .$$

The boron ion implantation technology with the doping dose $N_{id} = 2 \cdot 10^{15} cm^{-2}$ formed PCH channels. The surface resistivity of the ion-doped tensorresistive layers is equal to $R_s = 85 Ohm/\square$. The experimentally measured temperature dependences $\kappa_{mcV}(T)$ and $\kappa_{mcI}(T)$ in Fig. 3.3 and Fig. 3.4 are characterized by smooth changes in the range up to the boundary temperature of the intrinsic conductivity start. κ are the relative values of the transfer coefficients :

$$\gamma_{mc} = \frac{K_{mc}(T) - K_{mc}(T_0)}{K_{mc}(T_0) \cdot (T - T_0)} \cdot 100\% \quad (10)$$

The values of resistivity ρ and geometrical parameters of the MC topological structure a , b , d_{ch} selected during the design determine the boundaries of the operating temperature range. Minimization of the geometrical parameters of the topological structure of the MS in Fig. 3.1 depends on the constraints on the minimum values of the contact areas b , length $(a - b)$, and width d_{ch} of the piezoresistive channels. Determination of the minimum size limitations b_{min} is related to the experimental dependence of the temperature instability parameter γ_{mc0} of the normalized null output K_{mco} on the change in the contact area "Al-Si" (Fig. 3.5). In Fig. 3.5 γ_{mc0} is equal to

$$\gamma_{mc0} = \frac{K_{mco}(T_{per}) - K_{mco}(T_0)}{K_{mco}(T_0) \cdot (T_{per} - T_0)} \cdot 100\% \quad (11)$$

The boundary value γ_{mc0} is assumed to be $V_{mco} = 0.03\%^\circ C$. Then the minimum contact dimensions b_k from the graph in Fig. 3.5 are equal to $b_c = 20 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{cm}$.

Fig. 3.3 Temperature dependences of IPT sample parameters: I_{rev} reverse current: — - experimentally, — - calculated

For the idealized structure of an insulating p-n junction, it is assumed that the concentrations of ionized atoms determining the bulk charge region, and the electric field strength associated with them, are uniformly distributed in the direction of the axis coinciding with the metallurgical transition boundary [18, 19, 20]. In real p-n junctions, the concentration of ionized atoms must increase in the corners of the rectangular MC elements. This will change the parameters determining I_{0gen} and I_{Sgen} . That is, the reverse current I_{rev} must be dependent on the number of angles n in the topological structure of the MC. From n-type monocrystalline silicon wafer with orientation (001), test samples of beam force transducers (test-IPT) with different p-type MC (Fig. 3.6) geometric parameters were made. Fig. 3.7 shows the temperature dependences of the reverse currents for these structures according to the results of measurements.

Fig. 3.7 shows the results of investigation of influence of geometrical parameters of

Fig. 3.4 Temperature dependences of K_{mc0} - normalized null output, K_{mc}^v -IPT bridge sensitivity when $V_{in} = 5\text{ V}$ stabilized voltage is fed to the MC, K_{mc}^i - IPT bridge sensitivity when $I_{in} = 5\mu\text{A}$ stabilized current is fed to the MC

Fig. 3.5 Dependence of the temperature instability parameter γ_{mc0} of the normalized zero output of the bridge circuit (MC) on the contact size b_C .

Number	Structure	Topological MC Structure	Geometrical Parameters, cm				Number of Corners in the Structure on the Surface, n	A_{p-n}, cm^2	K_{p-n}
			a	b	d_{ch}	b_K			
#1			$60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$10 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$10 \cdot 10^{-4}$	32	$0,52 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1400
#2			$80 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$40 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	32	$0,96 \cdot 10^{-4}$	833
#4			$120 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$40 \cdot 10^{-4}$	32	$1,92 \cdot 10^{-4}$	667
#5			$140 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$80 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	32	$3,04 \cdot 10^{-4}$	526
#7			$120 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$40 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$40 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	8	$1,92 \cdot 10^{-4}$	500
#10			$R1 = 100 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$R2 = 60 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$40 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$20 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	500

Fig. 3.6 Topological structures and geometrical parameters of MC on test-IPT force transducer

topological structure on insulating properties of p-n junction. The temperature dependences of the reverse current densities $J_{rev}(T)$ of different test structures define three areas.

Fig. 3.7 Temperature dependences of the reverse current density of p-n junction insulating ion-alloyed and diffusion contact areas MC: --- - calculated from (3.10) \blacksquare - #1 ; + - #2; \blacktriangle - #4 ; \bullet - #5; \times - #7 ; \circ - #10

(A) The high-level region of inverse current density "A" is formed by the dependences for the structures, where the number n is maximal ($n = 32$), and K_{p-n} is in the range $800 - 1400$ (#1, #2). In this case, the extension of the upper bound of the operating temperature range to T_{per} values is unlikely. The insulating p-n junction areas need to be more than 3 times smaller than the previously determined limit value of the combined area of the four MC contact areas.

(B) The section of average values of J_{rev} "B" belong to the dependences of MC structures, where the number of corners n is 32 and 8 , but K_{p-n} is in the range of $(500 \div 700)cm^{-1}$ (#4, #5, #7). Here, the realistic design for high-temperature is MC #7 with parameters $K_{p-n} = 500 cm^{-1}$ and $n = 8$ with the area of p-n junction $A_{p-n} \leq 2 \cdot 10^{-4} cm^2$.

(C) Section "C", for the ring structure MC #10 with $K_{p-n} = 500 cm^{-1}$, at tempera-

tures $T > 180^\circ C$, is characterized by a good agreement with the calculated dependence $\mathbf{J}_{rev}(T)$. Differences at temperatures $T < 180^\circ C$ can be explained by the fact that in the calculations, in the dependence $\mathbf{J}_{rev}(T)$ selected the maximum limiting value S_0 , equal to $S_0 = 1 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cm/s}$. It is possible that in real MC the value of S_0 may be 100 times less.

Parameters and calculation relations for estimation of electro-physical characteristics of an ICP with an isolating p-n junction are equal: $R_{in}^{bc} = \frac{V_{in}}{I_{in}}$ — input impedance of the full-bridge circuit BC; $K_{mc0}^{bc} = \frac{V_{out0}}{V_{in}}$ — normalized null output BC; I_{rev} - reverse current at a reverse bias of insulating p-n junction by voltage 5 V ; $K_{pch} = \frac{V_{out} - V_{out0}}{V_{in} \cdot \epsilon_{x0}}$ strain-sensitivity coefficient of piezoresistive PCH [21], with assumed equality $|K_{\parallel}| = |K_{\perp}|$

$A_1; A_2$ — approximation coefficients of the temperature dependence of input resistance

$$R_{in}^{bc} = R_{in0}^{bc} [1 + A_1 (T - T_0) + A_2 (T - T_0)^2] \quad (12)$$

$K_A; K_B$ and K_C — approximation coefficients of the temperature dependence of the strain-sensitivity coefficient

$$K_{pch} = K_A + K_B \frac{T_0}{T} + K_C \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

Diffusion-alloyed test-IPT specimens with structure #7 determine values of coefficients of approximation of temperature dependences of strain sensitivity and resistance. Fig. 3.8 and Fig. 3.9 show experimentally obtained dependences of the coefficients.

The approximation coefficients of the ion doped PCHs were measured using test - IPT with the topological structures discussed in Fig. 3.6. The smallest scatter of the input resistances R^{br} , less than $\pm 2.5\%$, and the normalized null output K_{mc0} , less than $\pm 1.2mB/B$, were determined for #4 and #10. The values of approximation coefficients of temperature dependences of the strain-sensitivity coefficient and resistance for topological structures test-IPT of ion-alloyed PCH are given in Fig. 3.10. The performed calculations and experimental studies give grounds to assert that monolithic silicon integrated strain gauge transducers with isolation of PCH p-type conductivity from EE by p-n junction layer are workable up to temperature $(+180 \div +210)^\circ C$.

3.2 Monolithic IPT with distributed parameters

In monolithic IPT with distributed parameters (without insulation layer) the conductivity of MC is 1-2 times higher than that of EE. Thus, the bridge circuit electrically connects part of the elastic element material. In this case, the intrinsic conductivity tem-

Fig. 3.8 Dependences of the K_A ; K_B ; K_C approximation coefficients of the temperature dependences of the strain sensitivity PCH on the average resistivity PCH $\bar{\rho}_{ch}$, obtained from the research of the diffusion channels PCH.

Fig. 3.9 Dependences of approximation coefficients of temperature dependences of input resistance on average resistivity PCH , obtained from the research of diffusion channels PCH.

	K_A	K_B	K_C	$A_1, 1/K$	$A_2, 1/K^2$
#4	$10 \pm 5\%$	$60 \pm 8\%$	$-(14 \pm 3.6)$	$(1.14 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-3}$	$(1.5 \pm 0.4) \cdot 10^{-6}$
#10	$5 \pm 2\%$	$60 \pm 7\%$	$-(16 \pm 4)$	$(1.14 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-3}$	$(1.5 \pm 0.4) \cdot 10^{-6}$

Fig. 3.10 Values of approximation coefficients of temperature dependences of PCH strain-sensitivity $K_{mc}(T)$ and input resistance $R_{in}(T)$ for topological structures of test-IPT with ion-doped PCH.

perature T_{int} of the EE material determines the upper limit of the operating temperature range. At values $\rho_{ee} = (0.5 \div 20) \Omega \cdot cm$, T_{int} is equal from $325^\circ C$ to $+150^\circ C$.

Modeling and experimental researches were connected with the definition and studying of electro-physical characteristics of IPT at changing of values of resistance EE $\rho_{ee} = (0.5 \div 20) \Omega \cdot cm$ and temperature in the range of $0 - 300^\circ C$. The solution of the problem of constructing an IPT model with distributed parameters determines the relations for the design calculations [22].

The channels located in the volume of the silicon wafer of equal thickness H_{EE} form part of the measuring circuit. The condition $H_{EE} \ll a$ determines the uniformity of current distribution in the elastic element in the Z direction. The deformation transducer design is the best variant for modeling. A long line with parameters distributed along the X-axis (Fig. 3.11) defines the discrete analogue of the transducer model. The ratios for the load-sensitivity coefficient and the input resistance of the IPT with distributed parameters are:

$$K_{mc}^{dp}(T) = \frac{2 \cdot K_{pch}(T)}{2 + \frac{\bar{\rho}_{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \frac{H_{EE} \cdot \Phi}{x_j}} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{mc}^{dp}(T) = \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{2} \cdot \left[\frac{1 + \frac{\bar{\rho}_{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \frac{H_{EE} \cdot \Phi}{x_j}}{2 + \frac{\bar{\rho}_{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \frac{H_{EE} \cdot \Phi}{x_j}} + \frac{\bar{\rho}_{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \frac{H_{EE}}{2\sqrt{2} \cdot x_j} \right]^{-1} \quad (15)$$

where $K_{pch}(T)$ is the strain-sensitivity coefficient of electrically isolated PCHs with the temperature dependence defined by the second-degree polynomial (13); $\bar{\rho}_{ch}(T) = \bar{\rho}_{ch0} [1 + A_{ch1}(T - T_0) + A_{ch2}(T - T_0)^2]$ is the average resistivity of PCHs with the temperature dependence defined by the second-degree polynomial; $\rho_{ee}(T) = \rho_{ee0} \times [1 + A_{ee1}(T - T_0) + A_{ee2}(T - T_0)^2]$ is the resistivity of the silicon wafer with the temperature dependence defined by the polynomial of the second degree; x_j is the depth of PCH; Φ is the dimensionless coefficient, characterizing redistribution of the current of charge carriers in the PCH and part of the material EE; $R^{ch}(T)$ is the resistance of electrically isolated PCHs with the temperature dependence given by the polynomial of the second degree (12).

For any design of transducers of other mechanical quantities, the condition $a \leq H_{EE}$ is possible. In this case, the assumption of uniformity of current distribution in EE in the Z direction is inadequate to the nature of the distribution in the real object. Therefore, its effective value H_{ef} replaces H_{EE} . The parameter of overdistribution of the current of charge carriers in the channels (PCH) and the elastic element (EE) will

Fig. 3.11 Strain transducer along the X-axis selected to model the characteristics of the transducer with distributed parameters.

be equal:

$$\Lambda = \frac{H_{ef} \cdot b}{a - b} \cdot \Phi \quad (16)$$

Then, the ratios for the strain-sensitivity coefficient and the input resistance of the IPT with distributed parameters will be equal:

$$K_{mc}^{dp}(T) = \frac{2 \cdot K_{pch}(T)}{2 + \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \Lambda} \quad (17)$$

$$R_{mc}^{dp}(T) = \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{2} \cdot \left[\frac{1 + \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \Lambda}{2 + \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \Lambda} + \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)} \cdot \frac{\Lambda}{2\sqrt{2} \cdot \Phi} \right]^{-1} \quad (18)$$

Unification of the sensor design of a row of input mechanical quantities is related to the change in the IPT conversion characteristic by the choice of the thickness of the elastic element. The most convenient condition is the independence of $\frac{R_{mc}^{dp}}{R^{ch}}$ from the thickness H_{EE}

Fig. 3.12 shows the experimental dependence of the change in the input resistance MC on the design parameter $\frac{H_{EE}}{a}$. This condition will take place at $\frac{H_{EE}}{a} \geq 0.3$. The dependence of the parameter Λ on the resistivity ρ_{ee} was determined by test-IPT measurements with thickness $H_{EE} = 1 \cdot 10^{-2} cm$. The changes of Λ values for $\rho_{ee} = (0.5 \div 10) \Omega \cdot cm$ was within the measurement error. For the test-IPT, where PCHs were formed by boron ion implantation with a doping dose of $2 \cdot 10^{15} cm^{-2}$, $\Lambda = (9.1 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-3} cm$.

Fig. 3.12 Experimentally obtained dependences of the change in the coefficient Φ and the input resistance R_{mc}^{dp} on the design parameters for IPT with distributed parameters.

CHAPTER 4

Principles of Monolithic IPT design for the 0-300°C temperature range

The chapter presents the results of experimental research and evaluation of the effectiveness of the principles necessary for the design of specific structures of IPT, the results of the development and research of methods to minimize the systematic component of the intrinsic error, and the additional temperature error. Technological deviations of geometric dimensions reach values $\delta_{ee}^s = \pm 40\%$ and determine the systematic component of the intrinsic error δ_{ee}^s of miniature SPT with the thickness of elastic element $H_{EE} < 1 \cdot 10^{-2} cm$. Internal regulating elements and additional technological processes carry out adjustment of slope of IPT conversion characteristics [23]. Fig. 4.1 shows the tuning method for low-frequency beam accelerometers. Local anisotropic etching of the silicon wafer on the planar side forms areas of elastic elements and inertial mass. With anisotropic etching of the wafer on the planar side, the IE regions are divided into parallel bands with piezoresistive channels D1 and n tuning bands D2 without piezoresistors. The number of bands required for adjustment is removed without breaking the symmetry of the resilient element.

The data in [24, 25] describe the tuning by means of additional technological processes. Changing the thickness of EE in the process of shaping the transducer changes the slope of the pressure and acceleration transducer conversion characteristic. Periodically, in pauses of the etching process, the operator sets the silicon plate with IPT on the probe setup, loads the tested element (one or more) with a constant mechanical value and measures the electrical output signal (Fig. 4.2). The value of the selected output signal stops the etching process. The considered methods, without changing the electrical parameters, increase the yield by more than 10 times; reduce the systematic component of the intrinsic error by more than 10 times.

4.1 Monolithic IPTs with insulating p-n junction

According to the results of studies of temperature changes of the normalized null output $K_{mc0}(T)$, the additive component of the additional temperature error is $\gamma_{mco} = 0.04\%/^{\circ}C$. The standard value of additive temperature error for pressure transmit-

Fig. 4.1 A method for tuning low-frequency beam accelerometers.

Fig. 4.2 Setting IPT with the help of additional technological processes.

ters with a intrinsic error of $\pm 1\%$ is $0.06\%/^{\circ}C$ (for LF accelerometers with an intrinsic error of $\pm 5\%$, $0.1\%/^{\circ}C$). So, permissible value of multiplicative error component in case of temperature changes of strain-sensitivity coefficient $\kappa_{mcV}(T)$ should be $\gamma_{mc} = 0.04\%/^{\circ}C$ ($\gamma_{mc} = 0.07\%/^{\circ}C$ for accelerometers) [18, 26, 27]. When analyzing the conditions for the implementation of compensation for temperature changes in the conversion characteristic (multiplicative component), a differential temperature coefficient of sensitivity [16] equal to

$$\Gamma_{mc} = \frac{1}{K_{mc}(T)} \cdot \frac{dK_{mc}(T)}{dT} \quad (19)$$

The differential coefficient Γ_{mcV} determines the temperature changes in the conversion characteristic for an IPT with an isolating p-n junction if the stabilized voltage source

$$\Gamma_{mcV} = - \frac{K_B \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^2 + 2K_C \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^3}{T_0 \cdot \left[K_A + K_B \cdot \frac{T_0}{T} + K_C \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^2 \right]} \quad (20)$$

The condition of compensation for temperature changes of conversion characteristic is possible at $T = T_0$ if $K_B = K_C = 0$ (a) or $K_B = -2K_C$ (b). Condition (a) for diffusion PCHs is expected at values $\rho_{ee} < 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \Omega \cdot cm$ but, due to physical constraints in the form of limiting boron solubility, is not feasible. Condition (b) is not realized (as can be seen from the graph in Fig. 3.8). Similar conclusions are typical for IPT with ion-alloyed PCHs (see Fig. 3.10). When the bridge circuit is powered from a stabilized voltage source, the calculated values of temperature changes in the strain-sensitivity coefficient are: for diffusion channels $0.13\%/^{\circ}C$, for ion-alloy channels $0.12\%/^{\circ}C$.

Fig. 4.3 IPT wiring diagram with TCC

To create sensors with lower values it is necessary to apply a thermal compensation

circuit (TCC). The studied design of TCC contains trim resistors with TCR of different signs. Fig. 4.3 shows the circuit diagram of IPT with TCC, where R_{rs}^{tc} — regulating thin-film resistors of RS-1004 material, R_{si}^{tc} — regulating silicon p-type diffusion resistors with $\bar{\rho}_{si} = 7 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot cm$. The choice of TCC resistive elements is because thin-film resistors from RS1004 and diffusion resistors retain their characteristics in the same temperature range as the PCH of the IPT, i.e., $(0 \div +230)^{\circ}C$. The experimentally-fielded dependence of temperature changes of resistance of thin-film thermoresistors made of RS-1004 material formed on silicon wafers has the form [28, 29, 30] :

$$R_{rs}^{tc}(T) = R_{rs0}^{tc} \cdot [1 - 2,7 \cdot 10^{-3} (T - T_0) + 7,3 \cdot 10^{-6} (T - T_0)^2] \quad (21)$$

The experimental temperature dependence for the diffusion resistor R is as follows:

$$R_{si}^{tc}(T) = R_{si0}^{tc} \cdot [1 + 3,4 \cdot 10^{-3} (T - T_0) + 2,3 \cdot 10^{-6} (T - T_0)^2] \quad (22)$$

Calculation and modeling of the IPT with TSS of the transducer design with ion-doped channels considers the temperature variations of $R_{in}^{bc}(T)$ in Fig. 3.9. The channel resistance at $T = 25^{\circ}C$ is exactly $R_{in0}^{bc} = 1000 \Omega$.

$$R_{in}^{bc}(T) = R_{in0}^{bc} [1 + 1,1 \cdot 10^{-3} (T - T_0) + 1,5 \cdot 10^{-6} (T - T_0)^2] \quad (23)$$

Fig. 4.4 shows experimentally obtained in the temperature range of $(0 \div +230)^{\circ}C$ the dependences of changes in sensitivity k for IPT without compensation and with TCC. Connecting a TCC containing regulating resistors with positive and negative temperature coefficients made it possible to reduce the parameter γ_{mc} from $0,13\%/^{\circ}C$ to $0,015\%/^{\circ}C$. The articles [23, 31, 32] present the results of IPT studies in the temperature range $(-60 \div +80)^{\circ}C$ of physical and functional models with an isolating p-n junction for the case of powering MCs from a stabilized current source. The differential temperature coefficient of sensitivity for this case is equal:

$$\Gamma_{mcI} = \Gamma_{I0} + \Gamma_{I1} \cdot T + \Gamma_{I2} \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^2 + \Gamma_{I3} \cdot \left(\frac{T_0}{T}\right)^3 \quad (24)$$

where

$$\Gamma_{I1} = 2 \cdot \frac{K_A \cdot A_2}{K_A + K_B + K_C} \quad (25)$$

$$\Gamma_{I2} = \frac{K_B \left(A_1 - A_2 \cdot T_0 - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) - K_C \cdot (A_1 - 2A_2 \cdot T_0)}{R_A + R_B + R_C} \quad (26)$$

Fig. 4.4 Temperature dependences of the coefficient i IPT when supplied powered from a stabilized voltage source: 1 — IPT without compensation circuit 2 — IPT with TCC containing regulating resistors with TCR of different sign.

$$\Gamma_{I3} = 2 \cdot \frac{K_B \cdot \left(A_1 - A_2 \cdot T_0 - \frac{1}{T_0} \right)}{K_A + K_B + K_C} \quad (27)$$

The choice of optimal values of average resistivity in the range $\bar{\rho}_{ch} = (2 \cdot 10^{-2} \div 8 \cdot 10^{-2}) \Omega \cdot cm$ determines the compensation conditions of the IPT with a working temperature range $(0 \div +300)^0 C$. For the given values of $\gamma_{mc} \leq 0.04 \text{ \%}/^0 C$, the temperature operating ranges of an IPT with an insulating p-n junction are given in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2.

Table 4.1 IPT with lumped parameters for diffusion channels

#	Resistivity	Operating Temperature Ranges
1	$\bar{\rho}_{ch1} = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot cm$	$(-20 \div +180)^0 C$
2	$\bar{\rho}_{ch2} = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot cm$	$(0 \div +210)^0 C$
3	$\bar{\rho}_{ch3} = 4 \cdot 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot cm$	$(+50 \div +210)^0 C$

Table 4.2 IPT with lumped parameters for Ion-alloyed channels

#	Dose of doping	Operating Temperature Ranges
1	$N_{id} = 2 \cdot 10^{15} cm^{-2}$	$(+50 \div +210)^0 C$

Fig. 4.5 shows experimentally obtained in the temperature range dependences of the change in sensitivity for an IPT without TCC supply MC from a stabilized current source.

4.2 Monolithic IPTs with distributed parameters without insulating p-n junction

In the design of IPT with distributed parameters, EE is not only a link to convert the mechanical value. In addition, it is also an element for adjusting the temperature dependence of the output signal. The information about the change in the environment is completely accurate. It combines the functions of heat transfer and measuring circuit. Such a design increases the reliability of the sensor in the area of high (more than $200^0 C$) temperatures, because it does not require any element to adjust the characteristics, and parametric failure of the EE section is possible only simultaneously with its mechanical destruction.

Fig. 4.5 Temperature dependences of the bridge sensitivity K_{mcI} when powered from a stabilized current source for the MC:

— with diffusion channels; - - - with ion-alloy channels

Table 4.3 IPT with distributed parameters

#	Resistivity	Operating Temperature Ranges
1	$\rho_{ee1} = 10 \Omega \cdot cm$	$(-50 \div +200)^\circ C$
2	$\rho_{ee2} = 1 \Omega \cdot cm$	$(0 \div +300)^\circ C$
3	$\rho_{ee3} = 0.5 \Omega \cdot cm$	$(0 \div +325)^\circ C$

When supplying the IPT with distributed parameters from a stabilized voltage source, the differential temperature coefficient of strain-sensitivity taking into account the empirical temperature dependences for $K_{mc}^{dp}(T)$ is equal:

$$\Gamma_{mc}^{dp} = \Gamma_{mcV} - \frac{\Lambda \cdot \left[\frac{A_1^{ch} + 2A_2^{ch} \cdot (T - T_0)}{1 + A_1^{ch} \cdot (T - T_0) + A_2^{ch} \cdot (T - T_0)^2} - \frac{A_1^{ee} + 2A_2^{ee} \cdot (T - T_0)}{1 + A_1^{ee} \cdot (T - T_0) + A_2^{ee} \cdot (T - T_0)^2} \right] \cdot \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)}}{2 + \Lambda \cdot \frac{R^{ch}(T)}{\rho_{ee}(T)}} \quad (28)$$

where

$$\Gamma_{mcV} = - \frac{K_B \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right)^2 + 2K_C \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right)^3}{T_0 \left[K_A + K_B \frac{T_0}{T} + K_C \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (29)$$

differential temperature coefficient of strain-sensitivity for electrically isolated PCH with insulating p-n junction. Operating temperature ranges for IPT with distributed parameters without isolating p-n junction are presented in Table 4.3

For the design of small-sized sensors selected IPT design with distributed parameters with $\rho_{ee} = 1 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, for which in the range of $(0 \div +300)^\circ\text{C}$ experimentally determined the value of the parameter $\gamma_{mc0} = 0.04\% / ^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 4.6).

Fig. 4.6 Calculated (---) and experimentally obtained (----) temperature changes of strain-sensitivity coefficients for IPT with spread parameters ($K_{mc}^{dp}(T)$) and electrically isolated from EE PCH ($K_{mcV}(T)$)

CHAPTER 5

Creation of samples of small-size pressure and low-frequency acceleration sensors

Fig. 5.1 Static-dynamic pressure sensor

For the test systems of liquid rocket propulsion systems (LRPS) designed for reusable complexes, there is a lack of means for obtaining information about mechanical param-

Fig. 5.2 Low-frequency 0-300°C acceleration sensors

eters. In many cases, the test conditions require the lowest level of disturbing mechanical influences on the measuring instruments; obtaining information about processes and objects when the ambient temperature changes in the range of $0 - 300^{\circ}\text{C}$ [33, 34] .

The chapter shows the results of the research for the period 1983 – 1990 on the development of the design, manufacturing technology and evaluation of metrological characteristics of small-sized pressure and acceleration sensors for unit test systems[]. The obtained technical characteristics meet the requirements for the elements of CS, MS, RS of research and design-engineering, and finalization tests of the products in the Ministry of General Machine Building (now Roscosmos).

Figure 20 shows a static-dynamic pressure sensor from $0 \div 0.01 \text{ MPa}$ to $0 \div 1 \text{ MPa}$ with overall dimensions of $\varnothing 13 \times 11 \text{ mm}$ and weighing less than 10g containing monolithic IPT with distributed parameters (without insulating p-n junctions). An intrinsic error of less than $\pm 1\%$ and an additional temperature error of less than $0.05\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the temperature range $0 - 300^{\circ}\text{C}$ characterize the sensor [34].

Figure 21 shows low-frequency ($0 - 300 \text{ Hz}$) acceleration sensors *from* $0 \pm 10\text{g}$ to $0 \pm 30\text{g}$ with overall dimensions, containing monolithic ITP with insulating p-n junction. It is characterized by An intrinsic error of less than $\pm 5\%$ and an additional temperature error of $0.06 \text{ } \%/^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $0.13 \text{ } \%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperature range of operation is $0 - 200^{\circ}\text{C}$ [34, 35].

CHAPTER 6

Conclusion

6.1

The model of isolation of MC elements of monolithic IPTs by the united carriers of charge by p-n junction layer has been studied and the main regularities of influence of physical and geometrical parameters on the temperature dependence of isolating properties at temperatures more than $+100^{\circ}\text{C}$ have been established. It is experimentally confirmed that due to the decrease of the p-n junction area, the ratio of the perimeter to the junction area and the number of angles in the topological structure of MC elements the upper limit of the working temperature range is defined by the values more than $+200^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the temperature range of $0 + 250^{\circ}\text{C}$ the electrophysical characteristics were studied experimentally and the regular temperature dependences of strain-sensitivity factor and resistance were determined for monolithic IPT elements with insulating p-n junction produced by steady-state technological processes.

6.2

A physical and functional model of IPT deformation with MC with distributed parameters, PCH and CA doped with an impurity that increases the concentration level of the main EE charge carriers, providing the upper limit of the operating temperature range from 150°C to 350°C , is proposed. Using results of modeling and experimentally obtained parameter Λ characterizing redistribution of current of charge carriers in channels and EE volume, principles of IPT design of other mechanical quantities with design parameter $\frac{H_{EE}}{a} \geq 0.3$ are defined.

6.3

The effectiveness of the principles of minimization of the basic and additional temperature error of small-sized sensors with a range of operating temperatures in the range of $0 - 300^{\circ}\text{C}$ has been investigated and experimentally evaluated. To minimize the systematic component of the basic error, an accurate tuning method was developed and

experimentally investigated, in which the adjustment of the IPT conversion characteristic is carried out by changing the conversion coefficient EE . For the case of sensor supply with IPT with insulating p-n junction from stabilized voltage source, using experimentally obtained regular temperature changes of strain-sensitivity, input resistance of MC, diffusion and alloy RS-1004 resistance, the thermal compensation scheme was developed that allows to adjust IPT with high accuracy (less than $0.05\%/^{\circ}C$) in the temperature range $0 - +210^{\circ}C$. For the case of sensor supply with IPT with insulating p-p junction from stabilized current source, using experimentally obtained regular temperature changes of strain-sensitivity coefficient and output resistance MC the possibilities of "autothermocompensation" by selection of average value of specific resistance PCH and established temperature operation ranges in the range of $-20 - +210^{\circ}C$ have been studied. An experimentally accurate method of thermocompensation of sensitivity for temperature ranges of operation in the range of $-60 - 320^{\circ}C$ has been proposed and conducted, when the element regulating the temperature dependence of the IPT output signal with distributed parameters is a part of EE material with perfect information on the change in ambient temperature.

6.4

On the basis of the physical and functional models of IPTs substantiated in the work and the identified principles of their design, the designs, prototypes and measured metrological characteristics of pressure and acceleration sensors were created. The obtained technical characteristics meet the requirements for the elements of control, management and regulation systems for research and design-build tests of the industry products.

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